

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

INCLUDED IN THE CHAPTER STURNIDAE AND CROWS (CORVIDAE) OF THE FERNS SPECIES
COMPOSITION AND GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION OF BIRDS

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Abstract

In the article, along with the species composition and geographical distribution of birds belonging to the starling family, their reproduction, food character, migration sequence, etc. studied in detail. Including the change in the dynamics of the number of birds included in both families, the effects of anthropogenic factors on the way of life of those birds were compared to the previous years, and a general conclusion was reached. It has been known that the black sparrow, which belongs to the starling family, is a sedentary bird, and the blue sparrow is a nesting bird, and migrates after breeding. Among the birds belonging to the family of crows, zig-diz, ruddy raven, saridimdik raven, dalasha raven, gray raven and raven are sedentary birds. Only one species, the raven, is a wintering bird. Because it does not occur anywhere in the area during the breeding season. The wintering birds migrate at the end of March.

Keywords: anthropogenic, anthropic, autecology, polymorphic, monomorphic, reproduction.

From the ornithological studies conducted in different regions of the Autonomous Republic, it became clear that a large part of the birds distributed in the area live and breed in the Arazboyu plain. The Arazboyu belt, which forms the lowland zone of Nakhchivan MR, covers a large area of the Autonomous Republic located at an altitude of 600-1000 meters. This area starts from the Sadarak plain in the northeast and ends in Ordubad region. The plain area has different landscapes and favorable conditions for growth and feeding of ferns. Also, the abundance of solar radiation in the plain, the complexity of atmospheric circulation, and the variety of terrain play a major role in the widespread distribution of birds.

Our observations show that the number of birds in the plains increases significantly in autumn due to migratory birds and individuals making small migrations from the mountain belts. In the winter season, some of the sparrows (mainly sedentary birds) that live in the middle and high mountain zones make short trips to the Arazboyu plain to feed. Already in this period, an increase in species diversity of birds is observed. Nevertheless, the density of birds in the plain is very low compared to the breeding and migration period. It is clear from our long-term observations and literature materials that the number of birds in the Araz valley was once too high. During the last 50 years, large-scale economic measures, construction of buildings, construction of roads, canals and other anthropogenic factors in Nakhchivan, as in other parts of the world, have led to the deterioration of the living conditions of birds,

which has led to a sharp decrease in their number and species composition. However, it is commendable that the Arazboyu State Nature Reserve, created by the leadership of the Autonomous Republic in 2005 in 9 thousand 118 nectar areas, has been of exceptional importance in the protection of flora and fauna, including bird fauna.

The study of the bird fauna in Nakhchivan was started very late. Until the middle of the 20th century, there was no substantial research work on the study of bird fauna. As in Azerbaijan, which began in the middle of the 20th century, bird species in Nakhchivan have been partially specified, and the distribution and lifestyle of some of them have been studied in detail. For the first time, the avifauna of Nakhchivan was studied by A.I. Khanmammadov in 1955-1957 and valuable information was collected. The research work was carried out in different regions of Nakhchivan, especially in the Arazboyu plain, and it was determined that 190 species and subspecies of birds are distributed [1.p.6-22]. In 1965, Q.T. As a result of the research conducted by Mustafayev and A.I. Khanmammadov on the study of sparrows nesting in colonial and small groups in Nakhchivan, the collection of scientific evidence made it possible to reveal qualitative indicators as well as quantitative indicators of birds [10. p. 321-325]. Further studies on the study of the ornithofauna of Nakhchivan were conducted by H.M. Novruzov in 1978-2000, in addition, 28 species of birds were found to be distributed here. Also, the biotope, migration sequence, nest-

ing biology, plumage, etc. of these birds. studied in detail [6].

Starting from 2000, scientific employee of the Institute of Bioresources, Nakhchivan branch of ANAS, A.F. Mammadov, b.c.d., conducted extensive research on the study of avifauna and, in addition to discovering the spread of new species in the area, collected a lot of material on their biology by identifying the biotopes where they live [16.p.26-34]. A.F.Mammadov, as a result of his research work in 2000-2016, identified new species from the region for the avifauna of both Azerbaijan and the Republic of Moldova. According to the modern nomenclature, the systematic structure of these species has been specified, and it has been determined that they are sedentary or nesting species according to their reproduction indicators [15.p.62-69]. Thus, 18 groups, 54 families, 161 genera and 259 species have been identified in the ornithofauna of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, of which 64 species are included

in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The main purpose of the study of birds belonging to the family of sparrows and crows of the sparrow family was to review the ornithofauna of Nakhchivan. Because every 5-10 years there is a possibility of a change in the species composition of the fauna of any country or region. Especially since the territory of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is surrounded by 3 states, the possibility of new species in this region is higher. For this purpose, I decided to conduct a revisional study again, despite the fact that we conducted research on these chapters almost 30 years ago. The Arazboyu plain and foothill bushes, where ferns are most common, were taken as the place of study. It became clear from the researches that in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the family of starlings is represented by 2 species, and the family of crows by 8 species. Below is the distribution of those species by season and gender.

Table 1.

No.	Chapter	Genus	Type
1.	Sturnidae	1.Sturnus Linn, 1758	1.Sturnus vulgaris Linn, 1758
		2.Pastor Linn, 1758	1.Pastor roseus Linn, 1758
2.	Corvide	1.Garrulus Bris, 1760	1.Garrulus glandarius Linn, 1758
		2. Pica Bris, 1760	1. Pica pica Linn, 1758
		3. Purrhocorax Tunst, 1771	1. Purrhocorax purrhocorax Linn, 1758 2. Purrhocorax graculu Linn, 1776
		4. Corvus Linn, 1758	1.Corvus monedula Linn, 1758 2.Corvus frugilegus Linn, 1758 3.Corvus cornix Linn, 1758 4.Corvus corax Linn, 1758

Looking at the list, it becomes clear that there are 2 species of starlings and 8 species of crows in Nakhchivan, and most of them lead a sedentary lifestyle. Black starling- *Sturnus vulgaris*. (Linn, 1758). The main color is metallic black, the tail and wings are brown. They have white spots in autumn and winter. It is spread in Europe, Asia and North-West Africa. It migrates to the south of those continents to spend the winter. It is a polytypic species. The fauna of Nakhchivan includes 4 subspecies (s.v *vulgaris*; s.v *tauricus*; s.v *purpurasens* and s.v *caucasicus*). In winter, it moves from the northern regions of the territory to the southern part.

It is a sedentary bird in Nakhchivan. There are many birds in the territory of the Autonomous Republic, they start from the Araz river valley and spread up to 2200 meters above sea level. They usually breed in colonies, sometimes singly. They use tree wards, ravines and other suitable covered places for nesting. Sometimes the number of nests in one colony is 50-60. After breeding, these birds descend from the mountain belts to the Arazboyu plains. For this reason, they form large herds (500-1000 pieces) in the lowland region. The young calves of the cowherd are brown in color. In appearance, it looks like a blackbird, but it differs from it due to its short tail. In the spring, these birds turn

black, and in the fall, they are completely different from young individuals due to the formation of numerous white spots on their feathers [13. p. 222-231].

Pastorroseus. (Linn,1758)

Its range is located in Asia and Europe. It moves to the southern part of Asia to winter. It is a nesting bird in Nakhchivan. It migrates before breeding. It is considered one of the common and numerous birds during the nesting period. Migrating birds in May spread to all regions of the Autonomous Republic. However, they do not rise above 1800 m above sea level. Like the black sparrow, the blue sparrow builds a nest and reproduces singly or in colonies. On June 26, 2023, we came across a colony consisting of 38 nests in a ravine near Alincechay, Julfa district. After breeding, these birds spread to backyards and feed on berries and fruits, especially mulberries and grapes. They move in early August. In favorable years, small groups that remain until the end of September occur [4. p. 154-155].

Garrulus glandarius. (Linn, 1758)

Its area is Europe, Asia and North-West Africa. It is a sedentary bird in Nakhchivan. It is observed in all seasons of the year. It is mainly distributed in forests in the Autonomous Republic. Although it is rare in the upper zone of the forest, the number of ziggis increases as you go down to the foothills. On May 18, 2022, we

counted 22 zigzigs at a distance of 1 km in the lower zone of Bichenak forest, and 8 zigzigs at a distance of 1 km in the upper zone. In April-May 2023, we found 5 buzzard nests in Bichenak forest. The nests are built in an oak tree at a distance of 120-140 m from each other. The nests were 3-4 meters high from the ground. The owners of the nest were sleeping. After breeding, the young birds roam and feed together with the old ones. They form small herds in winter [10.p.268-269]. Common magpie - *Pica-pica* (Lynn, 1758).

Its range is located in Europe, Asia and North America. It is a sedentary bird in Nakhchivan. It is spread all over the Autonomous Republic. However, it is common in lowland regions and numerous in the foothills. Even during the nesting period, we met this bird in Khoshlu, Dubekli and Ganligol plateaus, which are 2500 meters above sea level. After the breeding season, it follows the herds of cattle in the pastures. In October and November, these birds come down from the mountains and gather in the plains, at the foot of the mountains, in the suburbs of cities and villages. Widely uses yard areas. It is an incomplete synanthrope. March is when the magpie divides into pairs and chooses nesting sites. Nesting pairs are often seen in late March and early April. On 18.04.2023, during observation in Nus-Nus garden of Ordubad district, most of the nests found contained 5-6 eggs. Mid-June coincides with the flight of magpie chicks. Parent birds feed and raise the chicks for an additional 15-20 days after they fly from the nest. They form small flocks in winter. There are 50-100 birds in a suitable roosting place [3. pp. 36-39].

Red-headed crow - *Pyrrhocorax pyrrhocorax*. (Lynn, 1758)

Its area covers Europe, Asia and North-West Africa. It is a sedentary bird in Nakhchivan, observed in all seasons of the year. It is spread in the alpine and subalpine zone of the mountains. The nest of this bird has been noted by us on Ilan dag, Ganli lake, Alinca castle and other heights. Nests are located on inaccessible rocks. After the breeding season, they descend from the mountains to the foothill valleys and plains. Even in October-November, it is often observed in the Araz-boyu plain. Sometimes they walk in herds and feed in agricultural fields.

Yellow mountain crane - *P. graculus*. (Lynn, 1758).

Its range is located in Europe, Asia and North-West Africa. It is a sedentary bird in Nakhchivan.

It is one of the typical bird species for the alpine belt of the Autonomous Republic. This bird is found in the high mountain zone of all regions. It also builds a nest on high rocks and forms a colony. The nests are in inaccessible places of high rocks. After the breeding season, they descend to the foothills. It can also be observed in the plains in the winter season.

Wandering crow - *Corvus monedula*. (Lynn, 1758).

Its range is located in Europe, Asia and North-West Africa. Although we did not happen to find that the wagtail built a nest and breed in Nakhchivan during our research 30-40 years ago, recently it has become one of the many birds, besides building a nest and giving birth. Especially in the Arazboyu plain, they prefer

to build nests and breed on electric poles. In winter, they combine with gray crows to form mixed flocks and forage together in agricultural fields. They are sedentary birds.

Zagcha crow - *C. frugilegus*. (Lynn, 1758)

Its area is located in Western Europe, Asia Minor, Iran, China and Japan. They are birds that winter in Nakhchivan. In the territory of the Autonomous Republic, the number of zaghjan increases during the spring and autumn migration period. In winter, it occurs in small groups (consisting of 5-7 individuals) in the lowlands. This bird is never seen during the breeding season. Overwintering birds migrate at the end of March.

Gray crow - *Corvus cornix*. (Lynn, 1758)

It is a polymorphic species. The fauna of Nakhchivan includes the nominal subspecies (*C. c. scharpii*). From the banks of the Araz River to the high mountains, it inhabits everywhere there are trees, bushes, steep rocks and ravines, including villages and cities. According to their lifestyle, they are birds of prey. Ducklings, chicks, kittens, etc. from the yard, hunts easily. They live in pairs during reproduction, and in flocks at other times. In natural conditions, it builds nests in bushes, reeds, trees, and in cultivated conditions only on tall trees. Recently, because the number of their natural enemies (birds of prey) has decreased, and because they are polyphagous, they feed on all living things and waste, and have increased rapidly. It can be said that they "captured" the city of Nakhchivan and all the greenery around it: gardens and parks. Since they spend the night in tall trees, they litter the surroundings and cause the tops of the trees to dry up. For this reason, there is a serious need to reduce the gray crow.

During the course of the research work, we studied for the first time the breeding biology of the gray crow in the city of Nakhchivan. In early spring, they divide into pairs and choose a nest site. They usually use old nests. Newly formed pairs build a new nest for themselves. Around the selected nesting area, pairs are often seen in that area for 10-15 days. If the nest is old, they restore that nest. For this purpose, the male individual carries dry tree branches, while the female individual collects them on the edges of the nest and reinforces it.

While observing 17 nests in the city of Nakhchivan, it became clear that crows mainly like to nest in large trees. The height of the nests from the ground reaches 10-15 meters. Most of these trees are sycamore, willow, elm, acacia, etc. was After the nests were ready, when taking their size, it was found that the volume of the newly built nests is smaller than the old nests. Because when old nests are repaired, their volume increases due to the litter added every year. When building the nest, its seat is built on thick branches of the tree, and the base of the nest is built from relatively dense dry branches. (1-1.5 cm in diameter.) The upper part is woven from thin twigs. After the nest is ready, its floor is covered with cotton, wool, feathers, fabric, etc. they lay.

Due to the size of the crow, the nest is not very large. Because when the turtle sleeps on the egg, it is easily visible from the outside. The average measurements we took from different nests were as follows: Di-

iameter of the nest: 32-66 cm, height: 20-43 cm, diameter of the bottom of the nest was 17-24 cm. After the nest is ready, in the middle of April, the female bird lays 4-5 greenish eggs with brown spots and lays eggs at intervals (10-15 days). The average size of the eggs was 38-41×28-31 mm. Hatching lasts 21 days, and the chicks hatched in the first half of May are fed and grown in the nest by the parent birds for a long time and leave the nest in mid-June.

Ravenclaw- *C. corax*. (Lynn, 1758)

Its area is wide, covering Europe, Asia, North Africa and North America. As in other regions of Azerbaijan, in Nakhchivan, they live in the middle and high mountain belts and build themselves nests on the rocks. During the breeding season, it occurs in the plateaus of Paradash, Batabat, Dübekli. In August 2022, in the territory of Julfa district, we came across chicks of this bird that can fly well. We assume that they came down from the mountain for food. In winter, when there is a thick snow cover, these birds descend to the lowland region of the republic. At this time, they can be observed around the villages and even in the city of Nakhchivan. We haven't seen a raven in the Araz Plain since March 20. Already in this period, they form pairs and climb to the high mountain belt to breed.

The result

The basis of the research work was the familiarization with the literature dedicated to the ornithofauna of Nakhchivan, as well as the materials obtained during our observations in different regions of the territory.

In addition to the Arazboyu plain, the observation object was occasionally visited in other regions of Nakhchivan, and materials were collected.

In addition to determining the species composition of birds belonging to the family of starlings and crows distributed in the territory of Nakhchivan MR, their seasonal variation, hatching, feeding, nesting, etc. necessary materials have been obtained. It has been known that the main mass of these birds live in different landscapes in areas up to 1500 meters above sea level, especially in the Arazboyu plain. In 2023, the vulture, which belongs to the family of crows, on which we conducted research, increased and built a nest and gave birth in Nakhchivan compared to 20 years ago. However, this bird has never been found nesting and breeding in this area before. Only a small number of wintering species were encountered. The main reason for this can be seen in the decrease of the natural enemies of these birds (birds of prey) and the change in climatic conditions.

The fauna of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is rich in scientific materials, and there is a serious need for its protection. Because as the anthropogenic landscape increases, birds, like all animals, are forced

to take refuge in certain areas, which leads to a decrease in the number of individuals in their population. If we compare the current situation with the observations we made 20 years ago, it is clearly noticeable that there is a significant decrease in the dynamics of the number of birds. In this regard, it is important to specify the number of rare and rare species, and to strictly monitor their habitats.

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